

DIAGNOSTIC AND TREATMENT LAPAROSCOPY IN ACUTE PANCREATITIS

Khojimetov D.Sh.

Aliboev M.R.

Andijan State Medical Institute

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Relevance. In recent years, diagnostic and therapeutic laparoscopy has become the generally accepted method of choice for enzymatic peritonitis caused by acute pancreatitis. It allows not only to clarify the form of pancreatic necrosis, the extent of the process and to carry out a differential diagnosis of acute pancreatitis with other acute surgical diseases of the abdominal organs, but also to remove effusion, perform sanitation of the abdominal cavity with washing it with the required amount of physiological solution. Laparoscopy makes it possible, under visual control, to adequately position drains in the abdominal cavity, providing conditions for complete drainage. Signs of biliary hypertension are an indication for laparoscopic cholecystostomy, which provides decompression of the bile ducts. If there are widespread fluid collections in the omental bursa, the mesentery of the small intestine, or along the ascending or descending colon, laparoscopy allows for their opening and drainage.

Target. To improve the results of treatment tactics for acute pancreatitis.

Materials and methods. In recent years, 73 patients with acute pancreatitis were treated at the Department of Emergency Endosurgery at the Andrei State Medical Institute clinic on the basis of the Department of Physics, 27 (36.9%) of them had severe pancreatic necrosis with a complicated course. Indications for laparoscopy were an increase in the phenomena of enzymatic peritonitis, an increase in the amount of free fluid in the abdominal cavity against the background of conservative treatment, as well as the need for differential diagnosis.

Results and their discussions. Laparoscopy was performed in 46 (63.1%) patients. Sanitation and diagnostic laparoscopy was effective in 34 (73.9%) patients; limited fluid collections formed in 5 (10.8%) cases. 7 (15.2%) patients died from progression of the destructive process in the pancreas and severe intoxication of the body.

Conclusion. Patients who underwent laparoscopic diagnosis and sanitation of abdominal drainage, compared with patients who underwent traditional surgery, noted earlier activation – 1,5 and 2 days, respectively, this led to a

decrease in postoperative complications (impaired pulmonary ventilation, purulent-inflammatory complications from the postoperative wound and abdominal cavity, early postoperative intestinal obstruction) was 2.1% versus 18.2% after traditional surgery.

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